

The Association of Nursing Home Staff and Resident Safety Outcomes: A Protocol for a Review of Reviews

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Abstract

Resident safety comprises an important topic for nursing practice with up to 33% of residents subjected to an adverse event amongst other safety-related outcomes. In spite of a large evidence base examining the relationship between nurse staffing and resident outcomes, the findings of several systematic reviews investigating the topic remain inconclusive and contradicting. A number of methodological weaknesses in the primary evidence (including cross-sectional study designs, aggregation and non-contemporary measures between exposure and outcome) and lacking causal models guiding analysis of different outcomes diminish meaningful interpretation of the results. The purpose of this review of reviews is thus to provide a comprehensive synthesis of the evidence on the association of direct care nursing home staff and specific resident safety outcomes in nursing homes. We will use descriptive and narrative synthesis to summarize the quantitative results of the relationship between staffing and outcomes. On a purposefully selected subsample of outcomes, we will use a pragmatically-guided narrative approach to extract information from the primary literature regarding explanatory models describing the nature of these relationships. For this analysis we use an inductive qualitative approach following the steps of a logic model to extract information on *input*, *activities*, *output*, *outcomes* and *impact* of a stated relationship. This review uses only previously published data and is exempted from an ethical board review. This study aims to advance the research on staffing and resident safety by providing a comprehensive summary and inform future research with regard to causal logic models guiding the analyses.

Background

Ever since *to err is human*, patient safety has gained attention in various healthcare settings including residential long-term care (Castle & Sonon, 2006). Given a frail and comorbid profile, the ever-growing nursing home population is particularly vulnerable to safety threatening events (Vincent, 2010). Evidence from a retrospective chart review indicates that up to 33% of residents are subjected to an adverse event (AE) within the first 35 days of their stay, two-thirds with temporary or lasting harm (Office of Inspector General & Levinson, 2014). Safety is formally defined by the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ) as “*a type of process or structure that reduces the probability of an adverse event*”. An adverse event or outcome is defined as harm to a resident as a result of medical care or in a health care setting (Simmons et al., 2016). While adverse event-detection is standard practice to assess and monitor safety in the hospital setting (Griffin & Resar, 2009), the focus in nursing homes is rather on resident safety related outcomes measured by quality of care indicators.

Nursing workforce plays a crucial role in providing and maintaining high quality and thus safe care delivery in both acute-care and long-term care setting (Brooks Carthon et al., 2019; Hughes (Ed.), 2008). Evidence from several primary studies and systematic reviews indicates that favorable resident outcomes are achieved with both higher total levels of nursing staff as well as higher skill-mix (Collier & Harrington, 2008; Dellefield, 2000). E.g., higher total levels or higher proportion of registered nurses (RNs) are associated with lower occurrence of pressure ulcers or weight loss (Bostick et al., 2006; Spilsbury et al., 2011). However, these findings are inconsistent and vary depending on the staffing measures, the staffing group (e.g., registered nurses, licensed practical nurses, nursing assistant, total staff) and on the type of outcomes (e.g., pressure ulcer, falls) measured (Armijo-Olivo et al., 2020). Two recently published reviews (Clemens et al., 2021; Tuinman et al., n.d.) further denote the topic’s timeliness. Yet, contradicting results on the association between staffing and resident safety-related outcomes impose a need for further investigation.

An additional challenge in examining the relationship between nursing home staff and resident safety is that “*safety outcomes per se have not been well studied in nursing homes*” (Simmons et al., 2016). The topic of resident safety is often approached broadly across publications where the terms “resident safety”, “resident safety (related) outcome”, “clinical outcome” and “quality of care” are used interchangeably. Accordingly, there is no common understanding what is included as safety outcomes in NHs. A recent study highlights the need to explicitly measure resident safety distinct from quality improvement initiatives such as Nursing Home Compare (25), a national database with regularly updated overall quality ratings and reports on quality indicators of US-NHs. The authors found a weak and inconsistent relationship between selected resident safety outcomes and an overall quality rating – and conclude that these publicly available databases do not provide sufficient information for judgement of resident safety (25). Additionally, a generic or overall measure of quality of care does not allow to specify logic models concerning the input, activities and outputs needed to guide an analysis on specific safety outcomes.

Rationale

In spite of a large evidence-base examining the relationship between nurse staffing and resident outcomes, the findings of several systematic reviews investigating the topic in the nursing home setting remain inconclusive and contradicting. A number of methodological weaknesses are commonly referenced in this context: The primary evidence builds often on cross-sectional studies, aggregated data (across time and individuals), non-contemporary measures between exposure (staffing) and outcome (e.g., clinical outcomes), thus prevailing any causal interpretation of the results (Armijo-Olivo et al., 2020; Tuinman et al., n.d.). Additionally, vastly differing operationalizations on both exposure and outcome as well as a lack of distinct logic models guiding the analysis of selected outcomes additionally diminish meaningful results. In order to advance the research on workforce and resident safety we propose this systematic review of reviews as follows.

Aim

The purpose of this review of reviews is to provide a comprehensive synthesis of the evidence on the association of direct care nursing home staff and resident safety outcomes in nursing homes. The following research questions are asked:

1. What resident safety outcomes are measured in the nursing home setting and how are they operationalized?
2. What staffing measures are assessed in relationship with resident safety outcomes and how are they operationalized?
3. What is the relationship of staffing measures with resident safety outcomes?
4. What explicit models/explanations are provided to explain the relationship between exposure (staffing) and selected outcomes? (We will make a purposeful selection of outcomes based on results from aims 1-3 with regard to their strength of evidence to pursue analysis of aim 4.)

Methodology

Protocol and registration

The protocol for this review of reviews was written following the PRISMA-P reporting guideline for protocols of systematic reviews (Moher et al., 2015) and the guidance offered by the Joanna Briggs' Institute: approach of conducting systematic reviews of association (Moola et al., 2015). The protocol will be published *a priori* on the web-platform Zenodo (European Organization For Nuclear Research & OpenAIRE, 2013). Prior to publication of this protocol, a preliminary search in PubMed was performed. Additionally, PROSPERO register, Johanna-Briggs-Institute (JBI) register of systematic reviews, Open Science Foundation OSF registry and Zenodo were screened for presence of a similar protocol to no avail.

Search strategy

We will search the following databases: Medline through PubMed, EMBASE and Cochrane Database. To account for recent reviews that are not yet indexed and databased, an additional search in Google Scholar will be conducted. Relevant key words of the topics "nursing staffing", "long-term care" and "systematic reviews" will be used to identify relevant titles. Results of an exploratory search indicated that the inclusion of the topic "resident safety outcomes" masks essential results. As described previously, within long-term-care literature the topic of resident safety is used interchangeably with its larger surrounding construct quality of care. Although recent initiatives strive for a uniform definition of resident safety (Simmons et al., 2016), this is not yet reflected in the literature. We thus decided to omit the topic "resident safety" (or its derivate, quality of care) from the search string and will instead capture the definition of the outcome solely within eligibility criteria.

The initial database to search will be PubMed, the search string will subsequently be translated for the other databases. Once all search strings are developed, they will be re-run concurrently on the same day with these final results being further processed. The search will be limited to review studies (filters: meta-analysis, review or systematic review), no restriction on dates will be applied. The development and execution of the search strategy is targeted for October 2021 - December 2021.

Eligibility criteria

The following eligibility criteria will be applied in the screening process:

Inclusion criteria

- Study type: Peer-reviewed systematic reviews that investigated the relationship between nursing home staff and resident safety outcomes or published white papers/government review reports with a systematic approach
- Outcome: We consider 'resident safety outcomes' as adverse clinical outcomes guided by the definition of an adverse event as "*harm as a result of medical care or treatment*" (Griffin & Resar, 2009). We extend the traditional understanding to include both harm as a result of commission as well as omission (Mangrum et al., 2020), as care omissions seem to be a key issue in the nursing home setting (Ogletree et al., 2020; Simmons et al., 2016). The adverse clinical outcomes have to be measured/reported in a resident-level database. Examples for resident safety outcomes which will be included are falls with injury, pressure ulcers, nosocomial infections. Contrarily, unintended weight loss – although putting the resident at high-risk for subsequent harm – will not be included.
- Population: Adult (> 18 years) residents living in a nursing home
- Setting: Nursing home/care home, residential long-term care, i.e., 24h care in an institution/residence by formal caregivers
- Exposure: Nursing home staff including direct-care nurses and care workers on different educational levels, social workers, activity staff and other staff involved in direct care. The staffing measures have to be measured/reported as an objective measure (e.g., number of nurses on a unit/per resident level).

Exclusion criteria

- Primary studies, qualitative reviews, editorials, letters to the editor, other white papers, non-published reviews
- Narrative reviews
- Exposure (staffing) is measured solely by perception-based measures of staffing studies (e.g., perceived staffing adequacy).

Data extraction and management

After duplicate removal, two researchers will independently screen titles and abstracts for their eligibility. Potential disagreement will be resolved by discussion with a third, more senior researcher. Data extraction on the included studies will be performed with a pre-tested and standardized extraction template (electronic spreadsheet) with - at least - the following information: full bibliographic information, authors, years of publication, number of included primary studies, risk of bias of included studies, country(ies) of included primary studies, design of included studies, population, sample size, resident safety outcomes, staffing measures, key results, explanations for association as well as comments by the reviewer.

Data extraction will be performed by a primary reviewer and checked by a secondary reviewer. Disagreement will be resolved in discussion, potentially with a third reviewer. We will not enquire any non-reported results from study authors.

Data will be managed using a shared Zotero library and decision steps will be documented in a text document.

Assessment of methodological quality of the reviews

Quality appraisal of the included reviews will be made using the SIGN *Methodology Checklist 1: Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses* (SIGN, 2021). SIGN is an initiative from Healthcare Improvement Scotland that offers several checklists to assess methodological quality of studies. The checklist is based on the AMSTAR tool (Shea et al., 2007). Compared with AMSTAR2 (Shea et al., 2017) the SIGN checklist allows to include all items for our study types and still preserve an overall rating of each study.

Rating of each study will be performed by a primary reviewer and confirmed by second reviewer. Disagreement will be resolved by discussion between the two reviewers. In case of persisting disagreement, a discussion with a third, senior researcher will be sought.

Data synthesis

Initially, the data collection process will be summarized with a PRISMA Flowchart (Page et al., 2021). Based on the heterogeneity of the existing literature, we do not anticipate any quantitative statistical synthesis. Instead, a narrative synthesis with several descriptive approaches such as tables and figures will be pursued for research questions 1-3. For the fourth research question – what explanation is offered to describe the relationship between exposure and selected outcomes – we will use a pragmatically guided two-step approach. Initially, the *discussion*-section of the included reviews will be screened to extract narrative information on offered explanations. As we do suspect only limited information provided to competently answer the research question, an additional step is taken based on the results from aim 2 and 3: For a selection of around two to four of the most prominent resident safety outcomes, an additional text analysis of a purposeful sample of underlying primary studies with a focus on *background*- and *discussion*-section will be conducted, as we anticipate logic models being emphasized there more prominently. In both steps, we will use a deductive qualitative methodology for text analysis and grouping. The extraction will be guided by the essential components of a logic model (Kellogg, 2004). Information will be grouped accordingly by “input”, “activities”, “outputs”, “outcomes” and “impact”.

Ethical consideration

There is no ethical approval needed for this type of study. We will only use data from previously published studies or reports.

Funding

The project is carried out mainly by a PhD-Student as part of their PhD-project. The student is appointed by the University of Basel. No further funding is sought.

Dissemination

This study aims to advance the research on staffing and resident safety by providing a comprehensive summary and inform future research with regard to causal logic models guiding future analyses. The results of this study are planned to be published in a peer-reviewed journal.

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